

Spectrophotometric and Conductometric Study of $UO_2(II)$ Complex of Quinizarin-2-sulphonic Acid

D. P. Joshi and D. V. Jain

$UO_2(II)$ ion with quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid forms a water-soluble, blackish violet complex in the ratio of 1:1 between pH range 3.95 and 4.50. The complex is stable between pH 3.09 and 6.0 and has maximum absorbance at 470 m μ . Molecular extinction coefficient, ϵ , comes to 5.008×10^4 at 570 m μ and 4.814×10^4 at 580 m μ and ionic concentration of 0.1 (NaCl).

In continuation of our work¹ on complexes of quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid (abbreviated as QSA) with $Fe(III)$, it has been observed that QSA also forms a blackish violet, water-soluble complex with uranyl ion. The complex is stable between pH range 3.09 and 6.0. QSA solution of $10.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ or further diluted obeys Beer's law at 570 m μ and 580 m μ at which complex formation has been studied. The absorbance of uranyl nitrate of $9.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ or further diluted is negligible at these wave lengths. The 1:1 ratio of the complex has been established spectrophotometrically, using, Job's method² of continued variations, mole-ratio method³, and slope-ratio method⁴. Conductance study, using the monovariation method⁵, also confirms the same ratio.

EXPERIMENTAL

Quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid used was of B.D.H. 'L.R.' quality and $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ was of 'AnalaR B.D.H. quality.

For preparing buffer solutions up to pH 6.0, sodium acetate and potassium chloride used were of AnalaR B.D.H. quality. HCl and acetic acid used were of chemically pure quality. Buffer solutions were prepared either according to the procedure adopted by Vogel⁶ or Findlay⁷. For spectrophotometric study, the pH was adjusted by buffering 10 ml of the mixed solution with 2 ml of the required buffer.

NaCl and $NaClO_4 \cdot H_2O$, used to maintain ionic concentration, were of AnalaR and chemically pure B.D.H. quality, respectively. Ionic concentration was adjusted by preparing the solutions in either 0.01 M $-NaClO_4$ or 0.1 M $-NaCl$ and diluting them to either 12 ml or 10 ml, respectively, with the same standard electrolyte solution.

1. Joshi and Jain, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 33.
2. *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, x, 8, 113.
3. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
4. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4498.
5. Nayar and Panda, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 284.
6. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 2nd ed., Longmans, 1960, p. 809.
7. Findlay, "Practical Physical Chemistry", 8th ed., Longmans, 1963, p. 268.

For absorbance, conductance, and pH measurements, the experimental set-up was the same as in our previous communication¹. The measurements were made after keeping the mixed solutions overnight.

Nature of the Complex Formed.—Application of the method of Vosburgh and Cooper² (Fig. 1) to the system $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ —QSA (in the ratio 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 UO_2^{++} to QSA), keeping the total volume at 12 ml and ionic concentration at 0.1 (NaCl), demonstrates the formation of only one complex because the region of maximum absorbance of QSA lies at 450 $m\mu$ (curve E), whereas those of the mixtures in 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 ratio of UO_2^{++} to QSA lie at 470 $m\mu$. Since the absorbance of QSA is less than that of the mixture only after 540 $m\mu$, 570 $m\mu$ and 580 $m\mu$ were selected for our study.

FIG. 1. Absorption spectra of mixtures of uranyl nitrate and QSA ($\mu=0.1$; NaCl).
 Curve A: $c=4.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=0.50$. Curve C: $c=1.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=2.0$.
 Curve B: $c=2.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=1.00$. Curve D: $c=0.66 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=3.0$
 (Curve E: $c'=2.00 \times 10^{-4} M$.)

FIG. 2
 $c=5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=1.0$.

Effect of pH on the Absorbance of the Complex.—Several solutions containing 10 ml of uranyl nitrate and quinizarin sulphonio acid, each of concentration $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ in the ratio of 1 : 1 and adjusted to different pH values by means of 2 ml of suitable buffers, were taken. Their absorbance was measured at 570 $m\mu$ and 580 $m\mu$. The range of constant absorbance was within the pH range of 4.00 to 4.58 (Fig. 2).

Effect of pH on the Composition of the Complex.—Application of Job's method of continued variations (Fig. 3) to the system $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ —QSA, keeping the total volume

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at 12 ml [10 ml of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 + QSA + 2$ ml of the required buffer], shows that 1:1 complex is stable between pH 3.00 and 6.0. The concentration of $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ as well as of QSA was $10.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. Observations at pH 1.00 and 2.0 do not lead to 1:1 ratio (Fig. 3, curves A and B).

FIG. 3. Effect of pH on the composition of uranyl-QSA complex at 570 mμ and 580 mμ (pH values shown on the curves). $c = 10.0 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 1.0$.

Stoichiometry of the Components.—The composition of the complex was established by the aforementioned methods¹⁻³. Observations in large number were taken. Some of the typical results are plotted in Fig. 4 to 8 and summarised in Table I where c represents the concentration of uranyl nitrate solution and p , the ratio c'/c (c' being the concentration of QSA solution). These measurements fall within the pH range 3.05 to 4.50 in which the complex has constant absorbance. In some cases, the exact pH has also been mentioned. The total volume was kept at 10 ml (metal+reagent) or 12 ml (10 ml of metal+reagent+2 ml of the buffer solution) for spectrophotometric study and 50 ml (metal+reagent) for conductometric study.

FIG. 4. By Job's method at 570 m μ & 580 m μ ($\mu=0.1$; NaCl).

Curve A: $c=9.00 \times 10^{-3} M$; $p=1.0$.

Curve B: $c=7.69 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=1.0$.

Curve C: $c=6.25 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=1.0$.

Curve D: $c=14.20 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=0.66$.

Curve E: $c=12.50 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=0.66$.

Molecular Extinction Coefficient by Slope-ratio Method.—Molecular extinction coefficient, ϵ , is equal to the slope of the straight line in which uranyl nitrate is varying. From Fig. 7, its mean value comes to 5.908×10^4 at 570 m μ and 4.814×10^4 at 580 m μ and ionic concentration 0.1 (NaCl).

 FIG. 5. By mole-ratio method at 570 $m\mu$ and 580 $m\mu$.

$pH=4.0$; $\mu=0.0083$ ($NaClO_4$).
 Curve A: $c=9.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=1.0$;
 fixed volume = 2.0 ml $UO_2(NO_3)_2$.
 Curve B: $c=6.68 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=1.0$;
 fixed volume = 2.0 ml $UO_2(NO_3)_2$.

 FIG. 6. By mole-ratio method at 570 $m\mu$ and 580 $m\mu$.

$\mu=0.1$ ($NaCl$).
 Curve A: $c=9.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=1.0$;
 fixed volume = 2.0 ml QSA.
 Curve B: $c=6.25 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p=1.0$;
 fixed volume = 2.0 ml of QSA.

TABLE I

Fig. No.	Curve No.	$c \times 10^{-4} M$.	p .	Fixed vol. of one component.	Vol. at the peak or inflection.	Vol. of metal+ reagent soln.	Composition of the complex $UO_2(n): QSA$.
By Job's method (equimol. soln.).							
4	A	9.000	1.0	..	5.0 ml	10.0 ml	1:1
4	B	7.692	1.0	..	5.0	10.0	1:1
	C	6.250	1.0	..	5.0	10.0	1:1
By Job's method (nonequimol. soln.). $\mu=0.1$ ($NaCl$).							
4	D	14.290	0.666	..	4.5	10.0	May be utilized to find out dissociation constant.
	E	12.500	0.668	..	4.6	10.0	
By mole-ratio method. $pH=4.0$; $\mu=0.0083$ ($NaClO_4$).							
5	A	9.000	1.0	2.0 ml $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	2.0	QSA 10.0	1:1
	B	6.668	1.0	2.0	2.0	10.0	1:1

TABLE I (contd.)

Fig. No.	Curve No.	$c \times 10^{-4} M$.	ρ .	Fixed vol. of one component.	Vol. at the peak or inflection.	Vol. of metal + reagent soln.	Composition of the complex $UO_2(x): QSA$.	
6	A	9.000	1.0	By mole-ratio method. $\mu=0.1$ (NaCl). 2.0 QSA		2.0 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	12.0	1:1
	B	6.666		2.0 "				
7	A	9.000	1.0	By slope-ratio method. $\mu=0.1$ (NaCl). 5.0		Parallel lines	10.0	1:1
	B	6.666		5.0				
8	A & A ₁	16.67	1.0	By monovariation method (direct & reverse titrations). 10.0 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ in direct titration & QSA in reverse titration.		10.0 QSA in direct titration & $20.0 UO_2(NO_3)_2$ in reverse titration.	50.0	1:1
	B & B ₁	12.50		20.0 QSA in reverse titration.				

FIG. 7. By slope ratio method at 570 & 580 mμ. $\mu=0.1$ (NaCl).

Curve A: $c=9.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $\rho=1.0$.
 Curve B: $c=6.66 \times 10^{-4} M$; $\rho=1.0$.
 Fixed volume in each = 5.0 ml.

FIG. 8. Conductometric titrations (direct and reverse).

Curve A & A₁: $c=16.67 \times 10^{-4} M$; $\rho=1.0$.
 Fixed volume for A + B = 10.0 ml.
 Curve B & B₁: $c=12.50 \times 10^{-4} M$; $\rho=1.0$.
 Fixed volume for A₁ + B₂ = 20.0 ml.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
 MEERUT COLLEGE, MEERUT.

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